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Biomedical and Biochemical Approaches and Strategies for Targeting and Delivery of Cadmium Oxide (CdO) Nanoparticles Aggregation Linked to DNA/RNA by Aryl Mercaptanes with Various Chain Length

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ABSTRACT

CdO nanoparticles show a strong peak of Plasmon absorption in ultraviolet-visible zone. A strong interaction exists between the surface of CdO nanoparticles and aryl mercaptan compounds. Aryl mercaptan compounds cause to aggregation of CdO nanoparticles linked to DNA/RNA and hence, lead to widening of peak Plasmon of CdO nanoparticles surface at 550 (nm) and emerging a new peak at higher wavelength. In the current project, this optical characteristic of CdO nanoparticles is used to time investigate of interaction between different aryl mercaptanes and CdO nanoparticles. The results were shown that aryl mercaptan compounds with shorter chain length interact faster with CdO nanoparticles. Therefore, a simple and fast method for identification of aryl mercaptanes with various chain length using red shift in surficial Plasmon absorption is presented.

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1. Introduction

Investigations about CdO nanoparticles are widely developed due to their considerable optical characteristics and potential application in optical devices, sensors and optical circuits specially in diagnostic and treating medical sciences [1–11]. CdO nanoparticles show a strong absorption peak in ultraviolet-visible zone when interact with light. The maximum position of spectrum depends on size, form, inter-particle space and de-electric environment of nanoparticles [12–21].

There is a high affinity between aryl groups and CdO nanoparticles which leads to aggregation of CdO nanoparticles linked to DNA/RNA. As a result of this aggregation, the Plasmon absorption peak of CdO nanoparticles widen at 550 (nm) and a new peak emerges at higher wavelength. Numerous researches have been performed about CdO nanoparticles aggregation linked to DNA/RNA and application of this characteristic of CdO nanoparticles for identification of target analytes and producing sensors [22–39].

In a research, chemical absorption of aryl mercaptans on CdO colloid at the presence of sodium hydroxide was investigated; the results were shown that the largeness of these changes depends on pH, chain length and the end of aryl mercaptans chain [40–56]. At another research, the effective factors on controlling the optical characteristics of CdO nanoparticles aggregation linked to DNA/RNA including oligonucleotides linked with various lengths (72–24 pairs) were studied. This test was shown that optical characteristics of DNA/RNA aggregation linked to CdO nanoparticles are controlled with size of aggregation and

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ignoring the chain length of oligonucleotides which is important for colorimetric identification based on nanoparticle, it was shown that optical effects are more dependent to size of aggregation which in turn, it is under kinetic control [57–69]. The rate of band change of surface Plasmon is conversely related to the length of DNA/RNA connections so that 24 chains systems (shortest) have shown the highest change in rate [70–81].

Mercaptanes are important compounds in chemical synthesizes, environment, gas and petrochemical industries and biology [82–99]. In the current research, optical characteristic of CdO nanoparticles is used to time identification of aryl mercaptanes with various chain length. In previously used methods for identification of mercaptanes in petrochemical and oil industry, only total mercaptan could be identified; however, the current method can identify mercaptanes with various chain lengths which is very important for making sensors of these compounds [100–156].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Preparing CdO Nanoparticles and Description of CdO Nanoparticles Aggregation Linked to DNA/RNA

All glass wears used in this test was washed with a solution of HCl: HNO₃ with concentration ratio of 3:1 and then, with deionized water and acetone and afterwards,

dried in air. In this project, Terkovic method was used for synthesizing the CdO nanoparticles. A 0.05 (gr) of hydrogen tetra coloro-urate (HCdCl₄, 3H₂O) was solved in 100 (ml) of water and then, was indirectly heated under 150 ° C temperature and stirring rate of 500 (rpm) in a balloon connected to a cooler. When CdO solution was boiled, 2.5 (ml) solution of sodium citrate of 0.05 (M) was added and the colloidal solution of CdO was gradually produced with reduction of CdO ions (III). The color of initial solution was mellow yellow. The color of this solution was gradually changed to blue, violet and dark red. At the end of test, the color was dark red. The size of produced nanoparticles was 25 (nm). The size of CdO nanoparticles was determined by DLS. In order to time investigate the interaction of CdO nanoparticles, aryl mercaptanes with various lengths were added to CdO nanoparticles at room temperature.

3. Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of CdO nanoparticles was recorded in various times with aryl mercaptans with various chain lengths as shown in Figures (1), (2) and (3). As can be seen in these figures, peak is decreased at 573 (nm) and a new peak is emerged at higher wavelength which gradually increased with time and after reaching to the maximum, the absorption decreases which is due to complete aggregation linked to DNA/RNA and instability of the produced CdO nanoparticles.

Fig. 1. (a) Absorption spectrum of CdO nanoparticles-phenyl mercaptan during 0–1200 (s)
(b) Absorption curve against time for CdO nanoparticles-phenyl mercaptan at maximum wavelength

Fig. 2. (a) Absorption spectrum of CdO nanoparticles-benzyl mercaptan during 0–1200 (s)

Fig. 3. (a) Absorption spectrum of CdO nanoparticles–propyl mercaptan during 0–1200 (s)
(b) Absorption curve against time for CdO nanoparticles–propyl mercaptan at maximum wavelength

The results show that aryl mercaptanes with shorter chain length lead to faster aggregation of CdO nanoparticles linked to DNA/RNA than ones with longer chain length. In other words, at shorter time, CdO nanoparticles is aggregated with aryl mercaptanes with shorter chain length at higher wavelength compared to absorption spectrum of CdO nanoparticles aggregated with aryl chains with longer

chain length. As can be seen in Figure (4), during 90 (s), phenyl mercaptanis emerged at higher wavelength (812.49 nm) than phenyl (777.91 nm) and pentylmercaptanes (a wide peak between 500–760 nm) and hence, aryl chains with various chain length can be identified through controlling the aggregation time.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectrum of CdO nanoparticles with various aryl mercaptanes during 90 (s) (concentration of CdNPs is equal to 250 ppm and 2.5 ml used, phenyl mercaptan 60 nmol, phenyl mercaptan 45.5 nmol and phenyl mercaptan 55.5 nmol).

The optical difference for aggregation of aryl mercaptanes connected to chains with various lengths to CdO nanoparticles can be attributed to size of aggregation linked to DNA/RNA and inter-particle distance.

4. Conclusion

In the current study, optical characteristics of peak Plasmon of absorption of CdO nanoparticles was used to identify mercaptanes with various chain length and through time controlling, they were identified successfully. It was observed that the second peak at wavelength between 500–760 (nm) induced by interaction of mercaptanes with CdO nanoparticles in aryl mercaptanes with shorter chain length

at shorter time duration observe at higher wavelength than aryl mercaptanes with longer wavelength.

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References

- Galindo-Rosales, F. J. Complex Fluids in Energy Dissipating Systems. *Appl. Sci.* 2016, 6 (8), 206, 10.3390/app6080206
- Tian, T.; Nakano, M. Design and Testing of a Rotational Brake with Shear Thickening Fluids. *Smart Mater. Struct.* 2017, 26 (3), 035038, 10.1088/1361-665X/aa5a2c
- Cohen, D. Shear-Thickening Fluid Reinforced Fabrics for Use with an Expandable Spacecraft; Patent No. US20080296435A1, 2008.
- Decker, M. J.; Halbach, C. J.; Nam, C. H.; Wagner, N. J.; Wetzel, E. D. Stab Resistance of Shear Thickening Fluid (Stf)-Treated Fabrics. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 2007, 67 (3-4), 565-578, 10.1016/j.compscitech.2006.08.007
- Lee, Y. S.; Wetzel, E. D.; Wagner, N. J. The Ballistic Impact Characteristics of Kevlar® Woven Fabrics Impregnated with a Colloidal Shear Thickening Fluid. *J. Mater. Sci.* 2003, 38 (13), 2825-2833, 10.1023/A:1024424200221
- Mewis, J.; Wagner, N. J. *Colloidal Suspension Rheology*; Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- Wagner, N. J.; Brady, J. F. Shear Thickening in Colloidal Dispersions. *Phys. Today* 2009, 62 (10), 27-32, 10.1063/1.3248476
- Brown, E.; Jaeger, H. M. Shear Thickening in Concentrated Suspensions: Phenomenology, Mechanisms and Relations to Jamming. *Rep. Prog. Phys.* 2014, 77 (4), 046602, 10.1088/0034-4885/77/4/046602
- Maranzano, B. J.; Wagner, N. J. The Effects of Particle-Size on Reversible Shear Thickening of Concentrated Colloidal Dispersions. *J. Chem. Phys.* 2001, 114 (23), 10514-10527, 10.1063/1.1373687
- Bender, J. W.; Wagner, N. J. Optical Measurement of the Contributions of Colloidal Forces to the Rheology of Concentrated Suspensions. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 1995, 172 (1), 171-184, 10.1006/jcis.1995.1240
- Bender, J.; Wagner, N. J. Reversible Shear Thickening in Monodisperse and Bidisperse Colloidal Dispersions. *J. Rheol.* 1996, 40 (5), 899-916, 10.1122/1.550767
- Foss, D. R.; Brady, J. F. Structure, Diffusion and Rheology of Brownian Suspensions by Stokesian Dynamics Simulation. *J. Fluid Mech.* 2000, 407, 167-200, 10.1017/S0022112099007557
- Seto, R.; Mari, R.; Morris, J. F.; Denn, M. M. Discontinuous Shear Thickening of Frictional Hard-Sphere Suspensions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2013, 111 (21), 218301, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.111.218301
- Guy, B.; Hermes, M.; Poon, W. Towards a Unified Description of the Rheology of Hard-Particle Suspensions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2015, 115 (8), 088304, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.115.088304
- Mari, R.; Seto, R.; Morris, J. F.; Denn, M. M. Shear Thickening, Frictionless and Frictional Rheologies in Non-Brownian Suspensions. *J. Rheol.* 2014, 58 (6), 1693-1724, 10.1122/1.4890747
- Clavaud, C.; Bérut, A.; Metzger, B.; Forterre, Y. Revealing the Frictional Transition in Shear-Thickening Suspensions. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 2017, 114, 5147, 10.1073/pnas.1703926114
- Royer, J. R.; Blair, D. L.; Hudson, S. D. Rheological Signature of Frictional Interactions in Shear Thickening Suspensions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2016, 116 (18), 188301, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.116.188301
- Comtet, J.; Chatté, G.; Niguès, A.; Bocquet, L.; Siria, A.; Colin, A. Pairwise Frictional Profile between Particles Determines Discontinuous Shear Thickening Transition in Non-Colloidal Suspensions. *Nat. Commun.* 2017, 8, 15633, 10.1038/ncomms15633
- Lin, N. Y.; Guy, B. M.; Hermes, M.; Ness, C.; Sun, J.; Poon, W. C.; Cohen, I. Hydrodynamic and Contact Contributions to Continuous Shear Thickening in Colloidal Suspensions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2015, 115 (22), 228304, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.115.228304
- Wyart, M.; Cates, M. E. Discontinuous Shear Thickening without Inertia in Dense Non-Brownian Suspensions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2014, 112 (9), 1, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.112.098302
- Cates, M. E.; Wittmer, J. P.; Bouchaud, J. P.; Claudin, P. Jamming, Force Chains, and Fragile Matter. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 1998, 81 (9), 1841-1844, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.81.1841
- Peters, I. R.; Majumdar, S.; Jaeger, H. M. Direct Observation of Dynamic Shear Jamming in Dense Suspensions. *Nature* 2016, 532 (7598), 214-217, 10.1038/nature17167
- Waitukaitis, S. R.; Jaeger, H. M. Impact-Activated Solidification of Dense Suspensions Via Dynamic Jamming Fronts. *Nature* 2012, 487 (7406), 205-209, 10.1038/nature11187
- Han, E.; Peters, I. R.; Jaeger, H. M. High-Speed Ultrasound Imaging in Dense Suspensions Reveals Impact-Activated Solidification Due to Dynamic Shear Jamming. *Nat. Commun.* 2016, 7, 12243, 10.1038/ncomms12243
- Maranzano, B. J.; Wagner, N. J. The Effects of Interparticle Interactions and Particle Size on Reversible Shear Thickening: Hard-Sphere Colloidal Dispersions. *J. Rheol.* 2001, 45 (5), 1205-1222, 10.1122/1.1392295
- Egres, R. G.; Nettesheim, F.; Wagner, N. J. Rheo-Sans Investigation of Acicular-Precipitated Calcium Carbonate Colloidal Suspensions through the Shear Thickening Transition. *J. Rheol.* 2006, 50 (5), 685-709, 10.1122/1.2213245

27. Egres, R. G.; Wagner, N. J. The Rheology and Microstructure of Acicular Precipitated Calcium Carbonate Colloidal Suspensions through the Shear Thickening Transition. *J. Rheol.* 2005, 49 (3), 719–746, 10.1122/1.1895800
28. Brown, E.; Zhang, H.; Forman, N. A.; Maynor, B. W.; Betts, D. E.; DeSimone, J. M.; Jaeger, H. M. Shear Thickening and Jamming in Densely Packed Suspensions of Different Particle Shapes. *Phys. Rev. E* 2011, 84 (3), 031408, 10.1103/PhysRevE.84.031408
29. Raghavan, S. R.; Walls, H.; Khan, S. A. Rheology of Silica Dispersions in Organic Liquids: New Evidence for Solvation Forces Dictated by Hydrogen Bonding. *Langmuir* 2000, 16 (21), 7920–7930, 10.1021/la991548q
30. Gálvez, L. O.; de Beer, S.; van der Meer, D.; Pons, A. Dramatic Effect of Fluid Chemistry on Cornstarch Suspensions: Linking Particle Interactions to Macroscopic Rheology. *Phys. Rev. E: Stat. Phys., Plasmas, Fluids, Relat. Interdiscip. Top.* 2017, 95 (3), 030602, 10.1103/PhysRevE.95.030602
31. Chu, B.; Brady, A. T.; Mannhalter, B. D.; Salem, D. R. Effect of Silica Particle Surface Chemistry on the Shear Thickening Behaviour of Concentrated Colloidal Suspensions. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 2014, 47 (33), 335302, 10.1088/0022-3727/47/33/335302
32. Shan, L.; Tian, Y.; Jiang, J.; Zhang, X.; Meng, Y. Effects of Ph on Shear Thinning and Thickening Behaviors of Fumed Silica Suspensions. *Colloids Surf., A* 2015, 464, 1–7, 10.1016/j.colsurfa.2014.09.040
33. Krishnamurthy, L.-N.; Wagner, N. J.; Mewis, J. Shear Thickening in Polymer Stabilized Colloidal Dispersions. *J. Rheol.* 2005, 49 (6), 1347–1360, 10.1122/1.2039867
34. Shenoy, S. S.; Wagner, N. J. Influence of Medium Viscosity and Adsorbed Polymer on the Reversible Shear Thickening Transition in Concentrated Colloidal Dispersions. *Rheol. Acta* 2005, 44 (4), 360–371, 10.1007/s00397-004-0418-z
35. Brown, E.; Forman, N. A.; Orellana, C. S.; Zhang, H.; Maynor, B. W.; Betts, D. E.; DeSimone, J. M.; Jaeger, H. M. Generality of Shear Thickening in Dense Suspensions. *Nat. Mater.* 2010, 9 (3), 220–224, 10.1038/nmat2627
36. Gopalakrishnan, V.; Zukoski, C. Effect of Attractions on Shear Thickening in Dense Suspensions. *J. Rheol.* 2004, 48 (6), 1321–1344, 10.1122/1.1784785
37. Xu, K. Nonaqueous Liquid Electrolytes for Lithium-Based Rechargeable Batteries. *Chem. Rev.* 2004, 104 (10), 4303–4418, 10.1021/cr030203g
38. Ding, J.; Tian, T.; Meng, Q.; Guo, Z.; Li, W.; Zhang, P.; Ciacchi, F. T.; Huang, J.; Yang, W. Smart Multifunctional Fluids for Lithium Ion Batteries: Enhanced Rate Performance and Intrinsic Mechanical Protection. *Sci. Rep.* 2013, 3, 2485, 10.1038/srep02485
39. Veith, G. M.; Armstrong, B. L.; Wang, H.; Kalnaus, S.; Tenhaeff, W. E.; Patterson, M. L. Shear Thickening Electrolytes for High Impact Resistant Batteries. *ACS Energy Lett.* 2017, 2 (9), 2084–2088, 10.1021/acseenergylett.7b00511
40. Shen, B. H.; Veith, G. M.; Armstrong, B. L.; Tenhaeff, W. E.; Sacci, R. L. Predictive Design of Shear-Thickening Electrolytes for Safety Considerations. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 2017, 164 (12), A2547–A2551, 10.1149/2.1171712jes
41. Shen, B.; Armstrong, B. L.; Doucet, M.; Heroux, L.; Browning, J. F.; Agamalian, M.; Tenhaeff, W. E.; Veith, G. M. Shear Thickening Electrolyte Built from Sterically Stabilized Colloidal Particles. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2018, 10 (11), 9424–9434, 10.1021/acscami.7b19441
42. Murphy, R. P.; Hong, K. L.; Wagner, N. J. Thermoreversible Gels Composed of Colloidal Silica Rods with Short Range Attractions. *Langmuir* 2016, 32 (33), 8424–8435, 10.1021/acs.langmuir.6b02107
43. Belyakova, L. A.; Varvarin, A. M.; Lyashenko, D. Y.; Roik, N. V. Study of Interaction of Poly(1-Vinyl-2-Pyrrolidone) with a Surface of Highly Dispersed Amorphous Silica. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2003, 264 (1), 2–6, 10.1016/S0021-9797(03)00395-3
44. Ewoldt, R. H.; Johnston, M. T.; Caretta, L. M. Experimental Challenges of Shear Rheology: How to Avoid Bad Data. In *Complex Fluids in Biological Systems*; Springer, 2015; pp 207–241.
45. Mewis, J.; Wagner, N. J. Thixotropy. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2009, 147, 214–227, 10.1016/j.cis.2008.09.005
46. Pednekar, S.; Chun, J.; Morris, J. F. Simulation of Shear Thickening in Attractive Colloidal Suspensions. *Soft Matter* 2017, 13 (9), 1773–1779, 10.1039/C6SM02553F
47. Zaccarelli, E.; Poon, W. C. Colloidal Glasses and Gels: The Interplay of Bonding and Caging. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 2009, 106 (36), 15203–15208, 10.1073/pnas.0902294106
48. Faroughi, S. A.; Huber, C. A Generalized Equation for Rheology of Emulsions and Suspensions of Deformable Particles Subjected to Simple Shear at Low Reynolds Number. *Rheol. Acta* 2015, 54 (2), 85–108, 10.1007/s00397-014-0825-8
49. Cwalina, C. D.; Harrison, K. J.; Wagner, N. J. Rheology of Cubic Particles Suspended in a Newtonian Fluid. *Soft Matter* 2016, 12 (20), 4654–4665, 10.1039/C6SM00205F
50. Trappe, V.; Prasad, V.; Cipelletti, L.; Segre, P.; Weitz, D. Jamming Phase Diagram for Attractive Particles. *Nature* 2001, 411 (6839), 772, 10.1038/35081021
51. Philipse, A. P. The Random Contact Equation and Its Implications for (Colloidal) Rods in Packings, Suspensions, and Anisotropic Powders.

- Langmuir 1996, 12 (5), 1127–1133, 10.1021/la950671o
52. Krishnamurthy, L. N.; Wagner, N. J. Letter to the Editor: Comment on "Effect of Attractions on Shear Thickening in Dense Suspensions. *J. Rheol.* 2005, 49 (3), 799–803, 10.1122/1.1895797
53. Krishnamurthy, L.-n.; Wagner, N. J. The Influence of Weak Attractive Forces on the Microstructure and Rheology of Colloidal Dispersions. *J. Rheol.* 2005, 49 (2), 475–499, 10.1122/1.1859792
54. Eberle, A. P. R.; Castaneda-Priego, R.; Kim, J. M.; Wagner, N. J. Dynamical Arrest, Percolation, Gelation, and Glass Formation in Model Nanoparticle Dispersions with Thermoreversible Adhesive Interactions. *Langmuir* 2012, 28 (3), 1866–1878, 10.1021/la2035054
55. Gao, J.; Ndong, R. S.; Shiflett, M. B.; Wagner, N. J. Creating Nanoparticle Stability in Ionic Liquid [C4mim][Bf4] by Inducing Solvation Layering. *ACS Nano* 2015, 9 (3), 3243–3253, 10.1021/acsnano.5b00354
56. Xu, K. Nonaqueous Liquid Electrolytes for Lithium-Based Rechargeable Batteries. *Chem. Rev.* 2004, 104 (10), 4303–4417, 10.1021/cr030203g
57. Yoon, I.-N.; Song, H.-k.; Won, J.; Kang, Y. S. Shape Dependence of SiO₂ Nanomaterials in a Quasi-Solid Electrolyte for Application in Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells. *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2014, 118 (8), 3918–3924, 10.1021/jp4104454
58. Kuijk, A.; van Blaaderen, A.; Imhof, A. Synthesis of Monodisperse, Rodlike Silica Colloids with Tunable Aspect Ratio. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2011, 133 (8), 2346–2349, 10.1021/ja109524h
59. Lai, C. Y.; Trewyn, B. G.; Jęftinija, D. M.; Jęftinija, K.; Xu, S.; Jęftinija, S.; Lin, V. S. Y. A Mesoporous Silica Nanosphere-Based Carrier System with Chemically Removable CdS Nanoparticle Caps for Stimuli-Responsive Controlled Release of Neurotransmitters and Drug Molecules. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2003, 125, 4451–4459, 10.1021/ja028650l
60. Sinha, A.; Chakraborty, A.; Jana, N. R. Dextran-Gated, Multifunctional Mesoporous Nanoparticle for Glucose-Responsive and Targeted Drug Delivery. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2014, 6, 22183–22191, 10.1021/am505848p
61. Kurtoglu, Y. E.; Navath, R. S.; Wang, B.; Kannan, S.; Romero, R.; Kannan, R. M. Poly(amidoamine) Dendrimer-Drug Conjugates with Disulfide Linkages for Intracellular Drug Delivery. *Biomaterials* 2009, 30, 2112–2121, 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2008.12.054
62. Kesharwani, P.; Jain, K.; Jain, N. K. Dendrimer as Nanocarrier for Drug Delivery. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 2014, 39, 268–307, 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2013.07.005
63. Müller, R. H.; Mäder, K.; Gohla, S. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLN) for Controlled Drug Delivery-A Review of the State of the Art. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 2000, 50, 161–177, 10.1016/S0939-6411(00)00087-4
64. Muchow, M.; Maincent, P.; Müller, R. H. Lipid Nanoparticles with a Solid Matrix (SLN, NLC, LDC) for Oral Drug Delivery. *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.* 2008, 34, 1394–1405, 10.1080/03639040802130061
65. Bae, Y.; Fukushima, S.; Harada, A.; Kataoka, K. Design of Environment-Sensitive Supramolecular Assemblies for Intracellular Drug Delivery: Polymeric Micelles that are Responsive to Intracellular pH Change. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2003, 42, 4640–4643, 10.1002/anie.200250653
66. Nasongkla, N.; Bey, E.; Ren, J.; Ai, H.; Khemtong, C.; Guthi, J. S.; Chin, S. F.; Sherry, A. D.; Boothman, D. A.; Gao, J. Multifunctional Polymeric Micelles as Cancer-Targeted, MRI-Ultrasensitive Drug Delivery Systems. *Nano Lett.* 2006, 6, 2427–2430, 10.1021/nl061412u
67. Lian, T.; Ho, R. J. Y. Trends and Developments in Liposome Drug Delivery Systems. *J. Pharm. Sci.* 2001, 90, 667–680, 10.1002/jps.1023
68. Allen, T. M.; Cullis, P. R. Liposomal Drug Delivery Systems: From Concept to Clinical Applications. *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2013, 65, 36–48, 10.1016/j.addr.2012.09.037
69. Hamidi, M.; Azadi, A.; Rafiei, P. Hydrogel Nanoparticles in Drug Delivery. *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2008, 60, 1638–1649, 10.1016/j.addr.2008.08.002
70. Merino, S.; Martin, C.; Kostarelos, K.; Prato, M.; Vazquez, E. Nanocomposite Hydrogels: 3D Polymer-Nanoparticle Synergies for On-Demand Drug Delivery. *ACS Nano* 2015, 9, 4686–4697, 10.1021/acsnano.5b01433
71. Chilkoti, A.; Dreher, M. R.; Meyer, D. E.; Raucher, D. Targeted Drug Delivery by Thermally Responsive Polymers. *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2002, 54, 613–630, 10.1016/S0169-409X(02)00041-8
72. Sawant, R. M.; Hurley, J. P.; Salmaso, S.; Kale, A.; Tolcheva, E.; Levchenko, T. S.; Torchilin, V. P. SMART[™] Drug Delivery Systems: Double-Targeted pH-Responsive Pharmaceutical Nanocarriers. *Bioconjugate Chem.* 2006, 17, 943–949, 10.1021/bc060080h
73. Luo, Z.; Cai, K.; Hu, Y.; Zhao, L.; Liu, P.; Duan, L.; Yang, W. Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles End-Capped with Collagen: Redox-Responsive Nanoreservoirs for Targeted Drug Delivery. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2011, 50, 640–643, 10.1002/anie.201005061
74. Cheng, R.; Feng, F.; Meng, F.; Deng, C.; Feijen, J.; Zhong, Z. Glutathione-Responsive Nano-Vehicles as a Promising Platform for Targeted Intracellular Drug and Gene Delivery. *J. Controlled Release* 2011, 152, 2–12, 10.1016/j.jconrel.2011.01.030
75. Wang, Y.; Wei, G.; Zhang, X.; Xu, F.; Xiong, X.; Zhou, S. A Step-by-Step Multiple Stimuli-Responsive Nanoplatform for Enhancing Combined Chemophotodynamic Therapy. *Adv. Mater.* 2017, 29, 1605357, 10.1002/adma.201605357

76. Ulbrich, K.; Hola, K.; Subr, V.; Bakandritsos, A.; Tucek, J.; Zboril, R. Targeted Drug Delivery with Polymers and Magnetic Nanoparticles: Covalent and Noncovalent Approaches, Release Control, and Clinical Studies. *Chem. Rev.* 2016, 116, 5338–5431, 10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00589
77. Moradi, E.; Vllasaliu, D.; Garnett, M.; Falcone, F.; Stolnik, S. Ligand Density and Clustering Effects on Endocytosis of Folate Modified Nanoparticles. *RSC Adv.* 2012, 2, 3025–3033, 10.1039/c2ra01168a
78. Saha, A.; Basiruddin, S. K.; Maity, A. R.; Jana, N. R. Synthesis of Nanobioconjugates with a Controlled Average Number of Biomolecules between 1 and 100 per Nanoparticle and Observation of Multivalency Dependent Interaction with Proteins and Cells. *Langmuir* 2013, 29, 13917–13924, 10.1021/la402699a
79. Tang, Z.; Li, D.; Sun, H.; Guo, X.; Chen, Y.; Zhou, S. Quantitative Control of Active Targeting of Nanocarriers to Tumor Cells Through Optimization of Folate Ligand Density. *Biomaterials* 2014, 35, 8015–8027, 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2014.05.091
80. Dalal, C.; Saha, A.; Jana, N. R. Nanoparticle Multivalency Directed Shifting of Cellular Uptake Mechanism. *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2016, 120, 6778–6786, 10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b11059
81. Dalal, C.; Jana, N. R. Multivalency Effect of TAT-Peptide-Functionalized Nanoparticle in Cellular Endocytosis and Subcellular Trafficking. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 2017, 121, 2942–2951, 10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b12182
82. Schmaljohann, D. Thermo- and pH-Responsive Polymers in Drug Delivery. *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2006, 58, 1655–1670, 10.1016/j.addr.2006.09.020
83. Gao, W.; Chan, J. M.; Farokhzad, O. C. pH-Responsive Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery. *Mol. Pharmaceutics* 2010, 7, 1913–1920, 10.1021/mp100253e
84. Saha, A.; Mohanta, S. C.; Deka, K.; Deb, P.; Devi, P. S. Surface-Engineered Multifunctional Eu:Gd₂O₃ Nanoplates for Targeted and pH-Responsive Drug Delivery and Imaging Applications. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2017, 9, 4126–4141, 10.1021/acsami.6b12804
85. Zhang, L.; Guo, R.; Yang, M.; Jiang, X.; Liu, B. Thermo and pH Dual-Responsive Nanoparticles for Anti-Cancer Drug Delivery. *Adv. Mater.* 2007, 19, 2988–2992, 10.1002/adma.200601817
86. Bikram, M.; West, J. L. Thermo-Responsive Systems for Controlled Drug Delivery. *Expert Opin. Drug Delivery* 2008, 5, 1077–1091, 10.1517/17425247.5.10.1077
87. Liu, J.; Detrembleur, C.; Debuigne, A.; De Pauw-Gillet, M. C.; Mornet, S.; Vander Elst, L.; Laurent, S.; Duguet, E.; Jerome, C. Glucose-, pH- and Thermo-responsive Nanogels Crosslinked by Functional Superparamagnetic Maghemite Nanoparticles as Innovative Drug Delivery Systems. *J. Mater. Chem. B* 2014, 2, 1009–1023, 10.1039/c3tb21272f
88. Luo, Z.; Cai, K.; Hu, Y.; Li, J.; Ding, X.; Zhang, B.; Xu, D.; Yang, W.; Liu, P. Redox-Responsive Molecular Nanoreservoirs for Controlled Intracellular Anticancer Drug Delivery Based on Magnetic Nanoparticles. *Adv. Mater.* 2012, 24, 431–435, 10.1002/adma.201103458
89. Wen, H.; Dong, C.; Dong, H.; Shen, A.; Xia, W.; Cai, X.; Song, Y.; Li, X.; Li, Y.; Shi, D. Engineered Redox-Responsive PEG Detachment Mechanism in PEGylated Nano-Graphene Oxide for Intracellular Drug Delivery. *Small* 2012, 8, 760–769, 10.1002/sml.201101613
90. Shao, Y.; Shi, C.; Xu, G.; Guo, D.; Luo, J. Photo and Redox Dual Responsive Reversibly Cross-Linked Nanocarrier for Efficient Tumor-Targeted Drug Delivery. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2014, 6, 10381–10392, 10.1021/am501913m
91. Shi, C.; Guo, X.; Qu, Q.; Tang, Z.; Wang, Y.; Zhou, S. Actively Targeted Delivery of Anticancer Drug to Tumor Cells by Redox-Responsive Star-Shaped Micelles. *Biomaterials* 2014, 35, 8711–8722, 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2014.06.036
92. Yui, N.; Okano, T.; Sakurai, Y. Photo-Responsive Degradation of Heterogeneous Hydrogels Comprising Crosslinked Hyaluronic Acid and Lipid Microspheres for Temporal Drug Delivery. *J. Controlled Release* 1993, 26, 141–145, 10.1016/0168-3659(93)90113-J
93. Mathiyazhakan, M.; Wiraja, C.; Xu, C. A Concise Review of Gold Nanoparticles-Based Photo-Responsive Liposomes for Controlled Drug Delivery. *Nano-Micro Lett.* 2018, 10, 10, 10.1007/s40820-017-0166-0
94. Yang, Y.; Aw, J.; Chen, K.; Liu, F.; Padmanabhan, P.; Hou, Y.; Cheng, Z.; Xing, B. Enzyme-Responsive Multifunctional Magnetic Nanoparticles for Tumor Intracellular Drug Delivery and Imaging. *Chem. - Asian J.* 2011, 6, 1381–1389, 10.1002/asia.201000905
95. Hu, Q.; Katti, P. S.; Gu, Z. Enzyme-Responsive Nanomaterials for Controlled Drug Delivery. *Nanoscale* 2014, 6, 12273–12286, 10.1039/C4NR04249B
96. Huang, J.; Shu, Q.; Wang, L.; Wu, H.; Wang, A. Y.; Mao, H. Layer-by-layer Assembled Milk Protein Coated Magnetic Nanoparticle Enabled Oral Drug Delivery with High Stability in Stomach and Enzyme-Responsive Release in Small Intestine. *Biomaterials* 2015, 39, 105–113, 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2014.10.059
97. Kim, J.; Kim, H. S.; Lee, N.; Kim, T.; Kim, H.; Yu, T.; Song, I. C.; Moon, W. K.; Hyeon, T. Multifunctional Uniform Nanoparticles Composed of a Magnetite Nanocrystal Core and a Mesoporous Silica Shell for Magnetic Resonance and Fluorescence Imaging and for Drug Delivery. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2008, 47, 8438–8441, 10.1002/anie.200802469
98. Liong, M.; Lu, J.; Kovoichich, M.; Xia, T.; Ruehm, S. G.; Nel, A. E.; Tamanoi, F.; Zink, J. I. Multifunctional

- Inorganic Nanoparticles for Imaging, Targeting, and Drug Delivery. *ACS Nano*2008, 2, 889–896, 10.1021/nn800072t
99. Taylor-Pashow, K. M. L.; Della Rocca, J.; Xie, Z.; Tran, S.; Lin, W. Postsynthetic Modifications of Iron-Carboxylate Nanoscale Metal–Organic Frameworks for Imaging and Drug Delivery. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*2009, 131, 14261–14263, 10.1021/ja906198y
100. Maity, A. R.; Saha, A.; Roy, A.; Jana, N. R. Folic Acid Functionalized Nanoparticles for Fluorescence-, Dark-Field-, and Dual-Imaging-Based Selective Detection of Cancer Cells and Tissue. *ChemPlusChem*2013, 78, 259–267, 10.1002/cplu.201200296
101. Sun, C.; Lee, J. S. H.; Zhang, M. Magnetic Nanoparticles in MR Imaging and Drug Delivery. *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.*2008, 60, 1252–1265, 10.1016/j.addr.2008.03.018
102. Yang, X.; Hong, H.; Grailer, J. J.; Rowland, I. J.; Javadi, A.; Hurley, S. A.; Xiao, Y.; Yang, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Nickles, R. J.; Cai, W.; Steeber, D. A.; Gong, S. cRGD-Functionalized, DOX-Conjugated, and ⁶⁴Cu-Labeled Superparamagnetic Iron Oxide Nanoparticles for Targeted Anticancer Drug Delivery and PET/MR Imaging. *Biomaterials*2011, 32, 4151–4160, 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2011.02.006
103. Mukai, H.; Ozaki, D.; Cui, Y.; Kuboyama, T.; Yamato-Nagata, H.; Onoe, K.; Takahashi, M.; Wada, Y.; Imanishi, T.; Kodama, T.; Obika, S.; Suzuki, M.; Doi, H.; Watanabe, Y. Quantitative Evaluation of the Improvement in the Pharmacokinetics of a Nucleic Acid Drug Delivery System by Dynamic PET Imaging with ¹⁸F-Incorporated Oligodeoxynucleotides. *J. Controlled Release*2014, 180, 92–99, 10.1016/j.jconrel.2014.02.014
104. Hendriks, B.; Shields, A.; Siegel, B. A.; Miller, K.; Munster, P.; Ma, C.; Campbell, K.; Moyo, V.; Wickham, T.; LoRusso, P. PET/CT Imaging of ⁶⁴Cu-Labeled HER2 Liposomal Doxorubicin (64Cu-MM-302) Quantifies Variability of Liposomal Drug Delivery to Diverse Tumor Lesions in HER2-Positive Breast Cancer Patients. *Ann. Oncol.*2014, 25, i19, 10.1093/annonc/mdu068.1
105. Lin, W.; Yao, N.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, L. pH-Sensitive Polymer-Gold Nanohybrid System for Antitumor Drug Delivery and CT Imaging. *J. Controlled Release*2017, 259, e14110.1016/j.jconrel.2017.03.286
106. Bridot, J. L.; Faure, A. C.; Laurent, S.; Riviere, C.; Billotey, C.; Hiba, B.; Janier, M.; Jossierand, V.; Coll, J. L.; Vander Elst, L.; Muller, R.; Roux, S.; Perriat, P.; Tillement, O. Hybrid Gadolinium Oxide Nanoparticles: Multimodal Contrast Agents for in Vivo Imaging. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*2007, 129, 5076–5084, 10.1021/ja068356j
107. Kim, J.; Piao, Y.; Hyeon, T. Multifunctional Nanostructured Materials for Multimodal Imaging, and Simultaneous Imaging and Therapy. *Chem. Soc. Rev.*2009, 38, 372–390, 10.1039/B709883A
108. Saha, A.; Basiruddin, S. K.; Sarkar, R.; Pradhan, N.; Jana, N. R. Functionalized Plasmonic-Fluorescent Nanoparticles for Imaging and Detection. *J. Phys. Chem. C*2009, 113, 18492–18498, 10.1021/jp904791h
109. Qi, J.; Han, M. S.; Chang, Y. C.; Tung, C. H. Developing Visible Fluorogenic ‘Click-On’ Dyes for Cellular Imaging. *Bioconjugate Chem.*2011, 22, 1758–1762, 10.1021/bc200282t
110. Zhu, S.; Yang, Q.; Antaris, A. L.; Yue, J.; Ma, Z.; Wang, H.; Huang, W.; Wan, H.; Wang, J.; Diao, S.; Zhang, B.; Li, X.; Zhong, Y.; Yu, K.; Hong, G.; Luo, J.; Liang, Y.; Dai, H. Molecular Imaging of Biological Systems with a Clickable Dye in the Broad 800- to 1,700-nm Near-Infrared Window. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*2017, 114, 962–967, 10.1073/pnas.1617990114
111. Bruchez, M., Jr.; Moronne, M.; Gin, P.; Weiss, S.; Alivisatos, A. P. Semiconductor Nanocrystals as Fluorescent Biological Labels. *Science*1998, 281, 2013–2016, 10.1126/science.281.5385.2013
112. Kim, S.; Lim, Y. T.; Soltész, E. G.; De Grand, A. M.; Lee, J.; Nakayama, A.; Parker, J. A.; Mihaljevic, T.; Laurence, R. G.; Dor, D. M.; Cohn, L. H.; Bawendi, M. G.; Frangioni, J. V. Near-Infrared Fluorescent Type II Quantum Dots for Sentinel Lymph Node Mapping. *Nat. Biotechnol.*2004, 22, 93–97, 10.1038/nbt920
113. Derfus, A. M.; Chan, W. C. W.; Bhatia, S. N. Intracellular Delivery of Quantum Dots for Live Cell Labeling and Organelle Tracking. *Adv. Mater.*2004, 16, 961–966, 10.1002/adma.200306111
114. Gnach, A.; Bednarkiewicz, A. Lanthanide-Doped Up-Converting Nanoparticles: Merits and Challenges. *Nano Today*2012, 7, 532–563, 10.1016/j.nantod.2012.10.006
115. Park, Y.; Kim, H. M.; Kim, J. H.; Moon, K. C.; Yoo, B.; Lee, K. T.; Lee, N.; Choi, Y.; Park, W.; Ling, D.; Na, K.; Moon, W. K.; Choi, S. H.; Park, H. S.; Yoon, S. Y.; Suh, Y. D.; Lee, S. H.; Hyeon, T. Theranostic Probe Based on Lanthanide-Doped Nanoparticles for Simultaneous In Vivo Dual-Modal Imaging and Photodynamic Therapy. *Adv. Mater.*2012, 24, 5755–5761, 10.1002/adma.201202433
117. Ray, S. C.; Saha, A.; Jana, N. R.; Sarkar, R. Fluorescent Carbon Nanoparticles: Synthesis, Characterization, and Bioimaging Application. *J. Phys. Chem. C*2009, 113, 18546–18551, 10.1021/jp905912n
118. Bhunia, S. K.; Saha, A.; Maity, A. R.; Ray, S. C.; Jana, N. R. Carbon Nanoparticle-based Fluorescent Bioimaging Probes. *Sci. Rep.*2013, 3, 1473, 10.1038/srep01473
119. Das, P.; Saha, A.; Maity, A. R.; Ray, S. C.; Jana, N. R. Silicon Nanoparticle based Fluorescent Biological Label via Low Temperature Thermal Degradation of Chloroalkylsilane. *Nanoscale*2013, 5, 5732–5737, 10.1039/c3nr00932g
120. Pan, D.; Zhang, J.; Li, Z.; Wu, M. Hydrothermal Route for Cutting Graphene Sheets into Blue-Luminescent

- Graphene Quantum Dots. *Adv. Mater.* 2010, 22, 734–738, 10.1002/adma.200902825
121. Shen, J.; Zhu, Y.; Yang, X.; Li, C. Graphene Quantum Dots: Emergent Nanolights for Bioimaging, Sensors, Catalysis and Photovoltaic Devices. *Chem. Commun.* 2012, 48, 3686–3699, 10.1039/c2cc00110a
122. Renikuntla, B. R.; Rose, H. C.; Eldo, J.; Waggoner, A. S.; Armitage, B. A. Improved Photostability and Fluorescence Properties through Polyfluorination of a Cyanine Dye. *Org. Lett.* 2004, 6, 909–912, 10.1021/ol036081w
123. Guo, L.; Gai, F. Simple Method to Enhance the Photostability of the Fluorescence Reporter R6G for Prolonged Single Molecule Studies. *J. Phys. Chem. A* 2013, 117, 6164–6170, 10.1021/jp4003643
124. Grimm, J. B.; English, B. P.; Chen, J.; Slaughter, J. P.; Zhang, Z.; Revyakin, A.; Patel, R.; Macklin, J. J.; Normanno, D.; Singer, R. H.; Lionnet, T.; Lavis, L. D. A general method to improve fluorophores for live-cell and single-molecule microscopy. *Nat. Methods* 2015, 12, 244–250, 10.1038/nmeth.3256
125. Jiao, L.; Song, F.; Zhang, B.; Ning, H.; Cui, J.; Peng, X. Improving the Brightness and Photostability of NIR Fluorescent Silica Nanoparticles Through Rational Fine-Tuning of the Covalent Encapsulation Methods. *J. Mater. Chem. B* 2017, 5, 5278–5283, 10.1039/C7TB00856B
126. Kim, J.; Lee, J. E.; Lee, J.; Yu, J. H.; Kim, B. C.; An, K.; Hwang, Y.; Shin, C. H.; Park, J. G.; Kim, J.; Hyeon, J.
127. T. Magnetic Fluorescent Delivery Vehicle Using Uniform Mesoporous Silica Spheres Embedded with Monodisperse Magnetic and Semiconductor Nanocrystals. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2006, 128, 688–689, 10.1021/ja0565875
128. Corr, S. A.; Rakovich, Y. P.; Gun'ko, Y. K. Multifunctional Magnetic-fluorescent Nanocomposites for Biomedical Applications. *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 2008, 3, 87–104, 10.1007/s11671-008-9122-8
129. Saha, A.; Basiruddin, S. K.; Pradhan, N.; Jana, N. R. Ligand Exchange Approach in Deriving Magnetic-Fluorescent and Magnetic-Plasmonic Hybrid Nanoparticle. *Langmuir* 2010, 26, 4351–4356, 10.1021/la903428r
130. Jin, Y.; Gao, X. Plasmonic Fluorescent Quantum Dots. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 2009, 4, 571–576, 10.1038/nnano.2009.193
131. Bigall, N. C.; Parak, W. J.; Dorfs, D. Fluorescent, Magnetic and Plasmonic-Hybrid Multifunctional Colloidal Nano Objects. *Nano Today* 2012, 7, 282–296, 10.1016/j.nantod.2012.06.007
132. Xu, Z.; Hou, Y.; Sun, S. Magnetic Core/Shell Fe₃O₄/Au and Fe₃O₄/Au/Ag Nanoparticles with Tunable Plasmonic Properties. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2007, 129, 8698–8699, 10.1021/ja073057v
133. Fan, Z.; Shelton, M.; Singh, A. K.; Senapati, D.; Khan, S. A.; Ray, P. C. Multifunctional Plasmonic Shell-Magnetic Core Nanoparticles for Targeted Diagnostics, Isolation, and Photothermal Destruction of Tumor Cells. *ACS Nano* 2012, 6, 1065–1073, 10.1021/nn2045246
134. Stankovich, S.; Dikin, D. A.; Dommett, G. H. B.; Kohlhaas, K. M.; Zimney, E. J.; Stach, E. A.; Piner, R. D.; Nguyen, S. T.; Ruoff, R. S. Graphene-Based Composite Materials. *Nature* 2006, 442, 282–286, 10.1038/nature04969
135. Huang, X.; Qi, X.; Boey, F.; Zhang, H. Graphene-Based Composites. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2012, 41, 666–686, 10.1039/C1CS15078B
136. Jiang, J.; Gu, H.; Shao, H.; Devlin, E.; Papaefthymiou, G. C.; Ying, J. Y. Bifunctional Fe₃O₄-Ag Heterodimer Nanoparticles for Two-Photon Fluorescence Imaging and Magnetic Manipulation. *Adv. Mater.* 2008, 20, 4403–4407, 10.1002/adma.200800498
137. Deng, S.; Ruan, G.; Han, N.; Winter, J. O. Interactions in Fluorescent-Magnetic Heterodimer Nanocomposites. *Nanotechnology* 2010, 21, 145605, 10.1088/0957-4484/21/14/145605
138. Basiruddin, S. K.; Saha, A.; Pradhan, N.; Jana, N. R. Advances in Coating Chemistry in Deriving Soluble Functional Nanoparticle. *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2010, 114, 11009–11017, 10.1021/jp100844d
139. Jia, G.; You, H.; Liu, K.; Zheng, Y.; Guo, N.; Zhang, H. Highly Uniform Gd₂O₃ Hollow Microspheres: Template-Directed Synthesis and Luminescence Properties. *Langmuir* 2010, 26, 5122–5128, 10.1021/la903584j
140. Ahren, M.; Selegard, L.; Klasson, A.; Soderlind, F.; Abrikosova, N.; Skoglund, C.; Bengtsson, T.; Engstrom, M.; Kall, P. O.; Uvdal, K. Synthesis and Characterization of PEGylated Gd₂O₃ Nanoparticles for MRI Contrast Enhancement. *Langmuir* 2010, 26, 5753–5762, 10.1021/la903566y
141. Dosev, D.; Nichkova, M.; Liu, M.; Guo, B.; Liu, G. Y.; Hammock, B. D.; Kennedy, I. M. Application of Luminescent Eu:Gd₂O₃ Nanoparticles to the Visualization of Protein Micropatterns. *J. Biomed. Opt.* 2005, 10, 064006, 10.1117/1.2136347
142. Paik, T.; Gordon, T. R.; Prantner, A. M.; Yun, H.; Murray, C. B. Designing Tripodal and Triangular Gadolinium Oxide Nanoplates and Self-Assembled Nanofibrils as Potential Multimodal Bioimaging Probes. *ACS Nano* 2013, 7, 2850–2859, 10.1021/nn4004583
143. Zhou, C.; Wu, H.; Huang, C.; Wang, M.; Jia, N. Facile Synthesis of Single-Phase Mesoporous Gd₂O₃:Eu Nanorods and Their Application for Drug Delivery and Multimodal Imaging. *Part. Part. Syst. Charact.* 2014, 31, 675–684, 10.1002/ppsc.201300342
144. Kim, W. J.; Gwag, J. S.; Kang, J. G.; Sohn, Y. Photoluminescence Imaging of Eu(III), Eu(III)/Ag, Eu(III)/Tb(III), and Eu(III)/Tb(III)/Ag-Doped Gd(OH)₃ and Gd₂O₃ Nanorods. *Ceram. Int.* 2014, 40, 12035–

- 12044, 10.1016/j.ceramint.2014.04.043
145. Wawrzynczyk, D.; Samoc, M.; Nyk, M. Controlled Synthesis of Luminescent Gd₂O₃:Eu³⁺ Nanoparticles by Alkali Ion Doping. *CrystEngComm* 2015, 17, 1997–2003, 10.1039/C4CE02500H
146. Geng, Y.; Dalhaimer, P.; Cai, S.; Tsai, R.; Tewari, M.; Minko, T.; Discher, D. E. Shape Effects of Filaments versus Spherical Particles in Flow and Drug Delivery. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 2007, 2, 249–255, 10.1038/nnano.2007.70
147. Toy, R.; Peiris, P. M.; Ghaghada, K. B.; Karathanasis, E. Shaping Cancer Nanomedicine: The Effect of Particle Shape on the in vivo Journey of Nanoparticles. *Nanomedicine* 2014, 9, 121–134, 10.2217/nnm.13.191
148. Godwin, A. K.; Meister, A.; O'dwyer, P. J.; Huang, C. S.; Hamilton, T. C.; Anderson, M. E. High Resistance to Cisplatin in Human Ovarian Cancer Cell Lines is Associated with Marked Increase of Glutathione Synthesis. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 1992, 89, 3070–3074, 10.1073/pnas.89.7.3070
149. Balendiran, G. K.; Dabur, R.; Fraser, D. The Role of Glutathione in Cancer. *Cell Biochem. Funct.* 2004, 22, 343–352, 10.1002/cbf.1149
150. Gronow, M. Studies on the Non-Protein Thiols of a Human Prostatic Cancer Cell Line: Glutathione Content. *Cancers* 2010, 2, 1092–1106, 10.3390/cancers2021092
151. Guo, X.; Wei, X.; Jing, Y.; Zhou, S. Size Changeable Nanocarriers with Nuclear Targeting for Effectively Overcoming Multidrug Resistance in Cancer Therapy. *Adv. Mater.* 2015, 27, 6450–6456, 10.1002/adma.201502865
152. Heidari, C. Brown, “Study of Composition and Morphology of Cadmium Oxide (CdO) Nanoparticles for Eliminating Cancer Cells”, *J Nanomed Res.*, Volume 2, Issue 5, 20 Pages, 2015.
153. Heidari, “Pharmacogenomics and Pharmacoproteomics Studies of Phosphodiesterase-5 (PDE5) Inhibitors and Paclitaxel Albumin-Stabilized Nanoparticles as Sandwiched Anti-Cancer Nano Drugs between Two DNA/RNA Molecules of Human Cancer Cells”, *J Pharmacogenomics Pharmacoproteomics* 7: e153, 2016.
154. Heidari, C. Brown, “Study of Surface Morphological, Phytochemical and Structural Characteristics of Rhodium (III) Oxide (Rh₂O₃) Nanoparticles”, *International Journal of Pharmacology, Phytochemistry and Ethnomedicine*, Volume 1, Issue 1, Pages 15–19, 2015.
155. Heidari, “Extraction and Preconcentration of N-Tolyl-Sulfonyl-Phosphoramid-Saeure-Dichlorid as an Anti-Cancer Drug from Plants: A Pharmacognosy Study”, *J Pharmacogn Nat Prod* 2: e103, 2016.
156. Heidari, “A Chemotherapeutic and Biospectroscopic Investigation of the Interaction of Double-Standard DNA/RNA-Binding Molecules with Cadmium Oxide (CdO) and Rhodium (III) Oxide (Rh₂O₃) Nanoparticles as Anti-Cancer Drugs for Cancer Cells’ Treatment”, *Chemo Open Access* 5: e129, 2016.
157. Heidari, “Linear and Non-Linear Quantitative Structure–Anti-Cancer–Activity Relationship (QSACAR) Study of Hydrous Ruthenium (IV) Oxide (RuO₂) Nanoparticles as Non-Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NNRTIs) and Anti-Cancer Nano Drugs”, *J Integr Oncol* 5: e110, 2016.
158. Heidari, “Genomics and Proteomics Studies of Zolpidem, Necopidem, Alpidem, Saripidem, Miroprofen, Zolimidine, Olprinone and Abafungin as Anti-Tumor, Peptide Antibiotics, Antiviral and Central Nervous System (CNS) Drugs”, *J Data Mining Genomics & Proteomics* 7: e125, 2016.